

Determinants of Utilization of Antenatal Care Services Amongst Women in Kenya: A Cross-Sectional Analysis of DHS Data

Aidan Reid

Abstract

Antenatal care (ANC) is defined as the care provided by skilled health-care professionals to women and adolescent girls who are pregnant in order to ensure the best possible health conditions for both the baby and mother (WHO). It is necessary for reducing maternal and infant morbidity and mortality rates. Despite vast improvements in Kenya's health infrastructure, ANC utilization remains subpar, with much needed improvement. The goal of this study is to analyze the different determinants and factors that affect the rate of ANC utilization by women, using data from the 2014 Kenya Demographic and Health Survey (DHS). This data was then cross-sectionally analysed on 14,942 women aged between 15–49 years of age who had given birth within the previous five years. A mixed methods approach was taken including both descriptive statistics along with binary logistic regression, which were used to assess associations between socio-economic and demographic factors affecting adequate ANC usage (≥ 4 ANC visits). The variables highly associated with adequate ANC usage are, having higher levels of maternal education, being located in urban residences compared to rural areas, and being wealthy rather than poor. Interventions promoting education and addressing economic barriers are essential for improving maternal and infant health outcomes in Kenya as a whole country.

Keywords: *antenatal care, maternal health, infant health, Kenya, DHS*

Introduction

Antenatal care (ANC) is one of, if not the most critical factor in ensuring proper health outcomes for both the mother and child, during and after childbirth for a few reasons. It allows for early detection of pregnancy-related complications and also lowers health associated risks for the mothers and their newborn infants. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a minimum of four ANC visits during pregnancy; that guideline has since been updated in 2016, recommending eight or more visits. However, in low- and middle-income countries such as Kenya, access to adequate ANC and healthcare in general remains a challenge and a severe barrier, therefore over 4 ANC visits is considered adequate.

In Kenya, according to the World Bank Group's most recent data of 2020, the maternal mortality ratio still remains far too high, with an estimated 530 deaths per 100,000 live births. Limited ANC visits contribute significantly to these negative outcomes for both the mother and child. This is because ANC provides essential services such as immunization, screening for infection and diseases, maternal nutritional guidance, and maternal birthing plans. However, barriers such as poverty, low education rates, cultural norms, and limited access to health care facilities present themselves as challenges that must be overcome in order to lower the maternal mortality ratio.

Prior research and the DHS data via statistical analysis highlights the role of education, household wealth, and rural versus urban residence in shaping health-seeking behaviors.

This study aims to examine factors associated with ANC utilization in Kenya using nationally representative DHS data. By identifying key socio-economic and demographic variables of ANC use, this report attempts to improve and shine light on equitable access to maternal healthcare in Kenya.

Methods

This study is based on data from the 2014 Kenya DHS. DHS is a program that assists developing countries via data collection and monitoring to evaluate population and health (DHS). The survey covered 14,942 women and adolescent girls aged 15-49, who have had at the very least one live birth in the five years preceding the survey.

This analysis considered several independent variables such as maternal age, education level, wealth index, and place of residence (urban vs rural). Descriptive statistics were used to determine how ANC utilization differed across the different variables mentioned. Binary logistic regression was used in order to assess the strength of associations between these multiple factors and to estimate adjusted odds ratios (AORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for the likelihood of attending at least four ANC visits.

The primary outcome of this analysis is to effectively determine which variables influence the usage rate of 4 or more ANC services amongst women and adolescent girls in Kenya.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Among the 14,942 women included, 54.47% attended four or more ANC visits during their most recent pregnancy. ANC use varied by age with the age range of 25-29 years having the highest utilization rate at 56.16% compared to the lowest age range at 15-19 years old with only 47.36% having 4 or more ANC visits. ANC use also varied by socio-economic and demographic characteristics. Women with higher education had the highest utilization rate (81.37%)

compared to only 40.9% among those with no education. Urban women were more likely to meet the recommended ANC threshold (63.08%) compared to rural women (49.93%). ANC rate was also affected by region. Nairobi, Kenya had the highest ANC utilization with 74.07% attending 4 or more ANC visits compared to the lowest being North Eastern Kenya at 37.45%. ANC utilization also increased with wealth, from 41.99% in the lowest income group to 73.08% in the richest.

Table 1
Descriptive Characteristics of ANC Utilization Among Kenyan Women

Variable	N	< 4 ANC Visits N = 6,803 ¹	≥ 4 ANC Visits N = 8,139 ¹	p-value²
age	14,942			<0.001
15-19		468.00 (52.64%)	421.00 (47.36%)	
20-24		1,574.00 (45.86%)	1,858.00 (54.14%)	
25-29		1,904.00 (43.84%)	2,439.00 (56.16%)	
30-34		1,315.00 (44.13%)	1,665.00 (55.87%)	
35-39		945.00 (46.37%)	1,093.00 (53.63%)	

40-44		457.00 (46.82%)	519.00 (53.18%)
45-49		140.00 (49.30%)	144.00 (50.70%)
region	14,942		<0.001
Central		450.00 (37.59%)	747.00 (62.41%)
Coast		732.00 (39.42%)	1,125.00 (60.58%)
Eastern		1,044.00 (45.45%)	1,253.00 (54.55%)
Nairobi		111.00 (25.93%)	317.00 (74.07%)
North Eastern		578.00 (62.55%)	346.00 (37.45%)
Nyanza		865.00 (41.53%)	1,218.00 (58.47%)
Rift Valley		2,376.00 (49.93%)	2,383.00 (50.07%)
Western		647.00 (46.31%)	750.00 (53.69%)
residence	14,942		<0.001

Rural		4,897.00 (50.07%)	4,883.00 (49.93%)
Urban		1,906.00 (36.92%)	3,256.00 (63.08%)
education	14,942		<0.001
Complete Primary		1,651.00 (43.56%)	2,139.00 (56.44%)
Complete Secondary		588.00 (33.37%)	1,174.00 (66.63%)
Higher		206.00 (18.63%)	900.00 (81.37%)
Incomplete Primary		2,103.00 (51.93%)	1,947.00 (48.07%)
Incomplete Secondary		609.00 (42.06%)	839.00 (57.94%)
No Education		1,646.00 (59.08%)	1,140.00 (40.92%)
wealth	14,942		<0.001
Middle		1,140.00 (43.40%)	1,487.00 (56.60%)

Poorer	1,504.00 (49.42%)	1,539.00 (50.58%)
Poorest	2,619.00 (58.01%)	1,896.00 (41.99%)
Richer	923.00 (37.44%)	1,542.00 (62.56%)
Richest	617.00 (26.92%)	1,675.00 (73.08%)

Binary Regression Results

Results of the binary regression analysis indicated that there are clear links between antenatal care use and the variables located in the table below. The first factor is education level. Women with a higher level of education were more than twice as likely to attend the recommended number of ANC visits (AOR = 2.57, 95% CI = 2.16-3.06). The second factor is wealth, women belonging to the wealthiest group were also more likely to use ANC (AOR = 1.41, 95% CI = 1.23-1.62). Another factor for utilization of ANC is the place of residence. Women living in urban areas were more likely to attend adequate ANC visits (AOR= 1.13, 95% CI=1.04-1.22). Age was also found as a factor influencing utilization, as women aged 40 to 44 were 32% more likely to utilize adequate ANC services (AOR=1.32, 95% CI = 1.09-1.59). The last variable that played a significant role in adequate ANC visits is the region. The highest prevalence of adequate ANC

visits was in the coastal region of Kenya, where women were 40% more likely to attend adequate ANC visits (AOR = 1.40 , 95% CI = 1.2-1.65).

Table 2

Adjusted Odds Ratios (AOR) for Determinants of Adequate ANC Utilization (\geq Four Visits)

Characteristic	OR [†]	95% CI [†]	p-value
age			
15-19	—	—	
20-24	1.20	1.03, 1.40	0.019
25-29	1.25	1.08, 1.45	0.004
30-34	1.26	1.08, 1.47	0.004
35-39	1.22	1.04, 1.43	0.018
40-44	1.32	1.09, 1.59	0.004
45-49	1.25	0.95, 1.65	0.12

region

Central	–	–	
Coast	1.40	1.20, 1.65	<0.001
Eastern	1.03	0.88, 1.19	0.7
Nairobi	1.25	0.97, 1.62	0.089
North Eastern	0.68	0.56, 0.83	<0.001
Nyanza	1.14	0.98, 1.32	0.10
Rift Valley	0.86	0.75, 0.98	0.027
Western	0.94	0.80, 1.11	0.5

residence

Rural	–	–	
Urban	1.13	1.04, 1.22	0.005

education

Complete Primary	—	—	
Complete Secondary	1.31	1.16, 1.48	<0.001
Higher	2.57	2.16, 3.06	<0.001
Incomplete Primary	0.81	0.74, 0.89	<0.001
Incomplete Secondary	1.04	0.92, 1.18	0.5
No Education	0.77	0.68, 0.87	<0.001

wealth

Middle	—	—	
Poorer	0.84	0.75, 0.93	0.001
Poorest	0.70	0.62, 0.78	<0.001
Richer	1.12	1.00, 1.26	0.056

Richest	1.41	1.23, 1.62	<0.001
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Discussion

This report demonstrates that socio-economic and demographic factors play a statistically relevant role in the impact of ANC utilization in Kenya. One of the most important predictors is educational level. Women who had at least completed secondary education were much more likely to attend four or more ANC visits. The reason behind this is up for debate however, a likely possibility is that they had greater awareness and understanding of the importance of ANC care for themselves and their unborn child.

Another critical factor that was statistically relevant was class status or wealth. Women in the richest group had notably higher odds of using adequate ANC services. This points out a clear discrepancy between wealth classes. Women who are poorer face barriers that those who are wealthy do not such as, transportation costs, clinic fees and having the necessary time to complete these visits. Policies and initiatives need to be put in place in order to help these women who struggle with the financial burden associated with ANC visits and those who cannot find the time to complete the visits due to lack of money.

The region where these women lived also played an important role. The findings showed that women located in urban residence lead to an increase in ANC utilization. This is likely due to a better healthcare infrastructure, shorter travel times, and more readily available health care services. To address the inequalities between rural and urban areas, investments in rural healthcare systems such as improved staffing and more clinics located in rural areas are essential to ensure equitable ANC services.

While age was a factor less strongly associated with ANC use as the others previously discussed, it still showed statistical significance. Younger women may encounter stigma, lack the necessary support, or are misinformed about the importance of ANC care. Programs can be put in place to educate young women on the importance of ANC in addition to support groups to ensure these young women are not alone in this critical time period.

Although Kenya in the past few years has made significant progress in their health care system, it is still not up to par according to the statistical findings in this report. In order to enhance maternal health outcomes in Kenya, interventions such as integrating health education, financial and emotional support, and infrastructure development are crucial to make ANC services equitable for all women who are pregnant.

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